

NATION BRANDING THROUGH JAMDANI

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Abstract

Nations across the world are taking different approaches to create a distinctive image about their countries or cities in the minds of people as such to create a national brand. Through nation branding countries thrive to attract tourists, accelerate inward investment, enhance export and maintain supportive diplomatic relationships. This paper focuses on Jamdani, a unique product of Bangladesh and analyzes how it may contribute in our nation branding. Thus, the aim of this article is to identify the unique features of Jamdani; explore its history and cultural heritage; the current market situation; analyze how Jamdani can contribute in nation branding; and lastly to provide a road map to brand Jamdani in international market. Both secondary and primary data are used for this exploratory research. For secondary data, different articles, books, and web-page were reviewed. For primary data BSCIC personnel in-charge of the Jamdani Palli and two large Jamdani retailers, were interviewed. Observation methods and informal discussion technique were applied at Jamdani Palli to have an overview of the weavers' livelihood, and artisan technologies. To evaluate the prospects of Jamdani towards nation branding, potentials of Jamdani were analyzed through Simon Anholt's (2003) six-dimensional model of nation branding. As a unique heritage product, originated from Bangladesh, Jamdani has got geographical indication (GI) in 2016. The multiple fine strings of different color with flora, fauna and geometrical shapes, and handmade weaving process are the unique features of this 600 years old product of cultural heritage. Presently, around 2000 weavers are producing around 60,000 jamdani products, fetching around \$40 lac from internal market and \$7 lac from international market. Given the potentials of Jamdani to nation branding this research proposes a road map to brand Jamdani in the international market following Keller, Pramassaran and Jacob's (2015) brand building block. Jamdani traders and other stakeholders can use the road map proposed in the paper as a practical guideline to present Jamdani in world market. This paper makes unique contribution to branding literature by analyzing a particular product through the lens of nation branding model and assimilating product/service branding strategies with nation branding.

Keywords : Brand Building Block, Cultural Heritage, Geographical Indication (GI), Nation Branding Hexagon.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The concept of 'Nation branding' introduced by the British brand practitioner Simon Anholt in 1996 has become one of the important topics of interest to different areas of researchers (Cheregi, 2018). Anholt (2013) asserted that the fame of countries, cities, and regions works like the brand images of products and firms, and this reputation is critical to the management, progress, and prosperity of those areas. Nations across the world are taking different approaches to create a distinctive image about their countries or cities in the minds of both local citizens and foreigners. There are three main reasons for which nations are making effort to enhance their country branding: to draw the attention of tourists, to accelerate inward investment, and to improve export (Dinnie, 2008).

According to American Marketing Association (AMA), "A brand is a name, term, design, symbol or any other feature that identifies one seller's goods or service as distinct from those of other sellers" ([Branding | American Marketing Association \(ama.org\)](https://www.ama.org)). When we associate the term brand with a nation, we mean some distinctive identity through which a country/nation positions itself in front of the global community as such to excel in international trade, attract flow of foreign funds in the form of investment, remittance and revenues from sale of products and services and promote positive diplomatic relationship (Nebenzahl, Jaffe and Usunier, 2003; Kleppe and Mossberg, 2006; and Yan, 2008).

In the context of globalization and increased interdependencies among the countries for survival and growth; individual countries and nations must present and maintain a positive national identity and image before the international community. Concerted efforts to build and communicate such an image can be coined as nation branding. Thus, Nation branding is seen from different angles, such as political marketing strategy (Varga, 2013), international public relations (Jordan, 2014), public diplomacy (Gilboa, 2008), social constructivism (Kaneva & Popescu, 2014), and marketing point of view (Buhmann & Ingenhoff, 2015). However, Anholt (2003) indicated six areas of national competence: culture and heritage, people, exports, investment and immigration, tourism and governance. The Bloom Consulting Index (2020) judge's brand's value of a country depending on five factors: investment, tourism, talent, country's reputation and exports. Some other elements are also considered for branding a nation, such as food, fashion, prominent personalities, etc.

Since the inception of the concept, like many other countries of the world, Bangladesh has taken initiative to create a national brand. The outcome is the launching of the tag line 'Beautiful Bangladesh' and a logo of rising sun from the waves of blue sea (Tinne, 2013). But this logo and tagline has not yet been widely publicized and recognized let alone improved Bangladesh's image among the international stakeholders. As per the Country Brand Index (Toursim) 2022 published by Bloom Consulting Bangladesh ranks 39 out of 46 Asian countries and 144 out of 203 countries around the globe. However, when the indexing is done in terms of trade, Bangladesh holds 17th position among 48 Asian countries and 45th among 206 countries across the world.

Literature focusing on branding Bangladesh mostly focused on the tourism sector or analyzed the country's prospect as a whole (Tinny, 2019; Tinne, 2013; Ahsan, 2013; and Hasan, Bhuiya and Kamruzzaman, 2013). Most Research papers focusing on Jamdani have highlighted its intricate quality, design and cultural heritage associated with it (Tabassum, 2021; Kumar, 2021; Karim & Karim, 2017 and Iqbal, 2014a). Researchers like Tabassum (2021), Bhattacharya (2014b) and Ghajnavi (2006) have demonstrated the traditional weaving technology, livelihood of the weavers. Others, such as Halder (2021) Karim & Karim (2017), Bhattacharya (2014a), and Iqbal (2014b) dedicated on the issue of GI on Jamdani and its implementations. None of these researches have evaluated Jamdani through lens of nation branding. The objective of this research is thus to evaluate prospects of Jamdani in nation branding. Specifically, this research intends to :

- a) identify the unique features of Jamdani in terms of the quality, texture of the fabric, intricated designs and themes;
- b) explore the history and cultural heritage associated with Jamdani;
- c) evaluate the current market situation;
- d) determine how Jamdani as a brand can contribute in nation branding; and
- e) to present a road map to brand jamdani in international market.

2. METHODOLOGY

Secondary as well as primary data are used for this qualitative exploratory research. Literature related to origin, history, cultural heritage of Jamdani fabric and its intricate designs and themes is reviewed thoroughly. Academic literature on branding, nation branding and its dimensions are also reviewed. Archived data from Bangladesh Small and Cottage Industries Corporation (BSCIC) were accessed to have an estimate of the current production and market size of Jamdani and its recent trends. Primary data are collected to get an updated view of the craft of Jamdani, its trading, and the potentials to associate it with national brand. Qualitative inquiries thriving to have an in-depth understanding of certain phenomenon can rely on small sample size. For a meaningful qualitative research information-rich sample and a thorough analysis of the information are more crucial than large sample size (Patton, 2002). Hence, In-depth interviews were conducted with purposively selected two large Jamdani retailers. BSCIC personnel in-charge of the Jamdani Palli at Narayanganj, Dhaka was interviewed. Observation and informal discussion technique were applied to have an overview of the weavers' livelihood, their community and artisan technologies. Primary data and most of the secondary data obtained from literature were thematically analyzed. The prospects of Jamdani in nation branding is analyzed using Simon Anholt's models of nation branding. Finally, to formulate the branding road map Keller, Pramesarn and Jacob's (2015) Brand building block is used.

3. UNIQUE FEATURES OF JAMDANI

Jamdani has been a coveted and adored fabric for hundreds of years with its history being rooted in the remote past. The researchers' observation of the Jamdani weaving in Noapara, Narayanganj area and conversation with the weavers reveal that

Jamdani produced in Bangladesh are completely handmade. Most of the materials used in weaving Jamdani are locally sourced and processed. Cotton yarn is produced in Madhobi region. Weavers purchase white (uncolored) yarn. Silk yarn comes from china and Jari yarn are produced locally while a portion comes from India. Local retailers sell all sorts of yarn and powdered color. As per requirement, the weavers make a mix of color and arrowroot and dip the bundles of yarn into the mix, rinse the liquid mixture out by twisting the bundle with hands and dry them in the sun. Sun dried color do not spill over.

Historically, Dhakai Jamdani or Jamdani weaved on the bank of the river Shitalakhya covering number of villages in Narayanganj and Sonargao region is well known for best quality Jamdani. According to Iqbal (2014a and 2014b), the reasons for concentration of Jamdani in this region. First of all, the area is located in the middle of places which produced 'shimul' cotton, a specific variety of cotton from which the delicate fine yarn is made to weave Jamdani. Second, the river system which facilitate the marketing activities like, supply of raw cotton and distribution and marketing of finished products. Third, the quality of the water of that area. The river 'Shitalakhya' was remarkable for the purity and coolness of its water. Since water was needed for processing cotton, it may be assumed that the water of Shitalakhya have some specific mineral mix that used to create the ambience to produce good quality yarn for Jamdani production. Fourth, the humidity of air in this region was found to be congenial. Too dry air may make the yarn hard and easily breakable on the other hand too much humidity may make the yarn too heavy to handle and make the texture kind of coarse. Fifth, the crisscrossing of rivers, which offered internal navigation and connected ports to the oceanic trade network.

The weavers and traders opined that Jamdani weaved in other geographical locations do not have the same texture and quality. Dhakai (Made-in-Bangladesh) Jamdanis have no coarse side. Both sides of the fabric are finely finished. It is really difficult to identify the front and back side of the fabric. On the contrary Indian Jamdanis are mostly machine-made, hence the back side of the fabric remains coarse which makes it uncomfortable to wear.

It is observed that flora, fauna and geometrical shapes are main themes of Jamdani. Weavers themselves create the designs being inspired by the nature and surrounding objects. Weavers and traders have validated these observations. However, the retailers interviewed reported that these days professional designers employed by big retailers are getting involved in the process. This intervention is somewhat good in terms of making the design trendy and modern while keeping the heritage associated with it.

While visiting the weaving facilities, the researchers have found that the weaving process is very intensive and time consuming. The weavers create the designs by using multiple fine strings of different color. The yarn / strings are so thin that one can barely see this with naked eye. Weavers, must have very good eye sight to craft the designs. They have to twist, turn and pull up and down at different angles to create the delicate designs. Handling the yarn with adept hands is also essential otherwise

the fine yarn will rip off. Typically, one master weaver and a helping weaver works over days to weave a piece of fabric. The time required to weave one 5.5-meter fabric (saree) depends on the design, and quality measured by the fineness of yarn or the number of yarns per centimeter length of the fabric (in other words ‘count’). Table 1 shows the required man-hour to weave Jamdani with different design and count.

Table 1 : Required Man-hour to Weave a Piece of Jamdani

Features of Jamdani		Man-hour Needed to Produce	
Design	Count	A Saree (5.5 m)	A Meter
Light floral/geometric design on the borders (‘parh’) and the edge (‘aanchol’) and lightly spread small floral/geometric shape (‘buti’) all-over.	50-60	150-250	28-45
	60-80	250-350	45-60
	80-100	350-450	60-80
Floral/geometric design only on the borders (‘parh’) and the edge (‘aanchol’) and moderately spread small floral/geometric shape (‘buti’) all-over	60-80	300-400	55-70
	80-100	400-500	70-90
Delicate floral/geometric design on the borders (‘parh’) and the edge (‘aanchol’) and gorgeous and densely spread floral/geometric shapes (‘buti’) all-over	80-100	700-800	125-145
	above	800-900	145-165
	100		

Source : Developed by the researchers based on information collected from the weavers and BSCIC personnel at Noapara, Narayanganj

Apart from the intricacy, variety, density (compactness) of design, and color combinations; the quality of Jamdani is determined by the fineness of yarn and the number of yarns per centimeter length of the fabric in other words ‘count’. Sophisticated fine design, matt color, fine finish on both sides and consistent smooth texture throughout are the special features of our Jamdani.

4. THE HISTORY AND CULTURAL HERITAGE ASSOCIATED WITH JAMDANI

‘Jamdani’ also known as ‘Dhakai Jamdani’ can be considered as one of the prides of Bengal whose history started at Sonargaon, the old capital of Bengal along the banks of river Sitalakhya in Bangladesh. The weaving culture of Jamdani is said to have begun in the Maurya period, c. 320 B.C.E. and gained popularity during the Akbarian era (Mughal Dynasty) and earned a flared recognition during the rule of Aurangzeb (Iqbal, 2014a; and Ghuznavi, 2006).

According to some historians, Jamdani is considered to be Persian origin. The name Jamdani is thought to be taken from two words ‘jam’ means ‘flower’ and ‘dani’ means ‘vase’. However, the history of Jamdani is outlined in the 3rd century, found in an ancient economics book, named Kautaliya’s Arthashastra, where it has been sketched as very delicate and transparent silk saree. It is found in different books that a saree was so thin that it could be channeled through any Match Box. In some books, Jamdani has

been considered as Muslin. But, in reality these two resembled different fabrics with different way of waving, though motifs are same in some cases. The present versions of Jamdanis are different from Muslins in terms of fineness, thread counts and even motifs (Bhattacharya, 2014a; Bhattacharya, 2014b; and Ghuznavi, 2006).

It is believed that the early weavers used to weave Jamdani for Muslims as they used to use motifs and patterns made up of geometric representations of non-animal images like flowers, and leaves, as to use images of animal is forbidden in Islam. The Sultan of Delhi Muhammad bin Tughlak brought some Persian weavers to weave Jamdani for Muslims in the 14th century in this sub-continent. As ecological climate such as temperature, level of humidity, quality of water with minerals, is very important for producing Jamdani, all weavers from Persia therefore carefully chosen the area in and around Dhaka in this sub-continent due to its specific geographic and ecological context. Sonargaon, the old capital of Dhaka was considered as uniquely important not only for ecological climate, but because of many reasons. It was also served as an important inland port connected Bengal with the Middle East and Far Eastern countries. Thus, Sonargaon and Narayanganj region was considered as a thriving center of trade and commerce according to numerous early travelers like Ibn Battuta (Iqbal, 2014a).

Thus, Dhaka's cotton products, especially muslin became a world-renowned item of trade of commerce in the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries (Kumar, 2021). The most elegant and expensive muslin was called MalbasKhas, locally called Jamdani which was especially manufactured for the Delhi emperor and his household. The Nawab of Bengal at that time sent MalbasKhas to the emperor as honors (Iqbal, 2014b). However, at the time of British colonialism, due to import policies favoring industrially manufactured textiles, the Jamdani and muslin industries rapidly declined. The import of cheaper and lower quality yarn from Europe also contributed behind this declination (Bhattacharya, 2014a).

With pace of time, Jamdani became popular in and around present Bangladesh. It catches the eyes of sophisticated, stylish, and elegant women of upper class of the society as Jamdani was symbol of aristocracy of that time. Jamdani became popular regardless of religion and became popular among all the women of this sub-continent. It stepped in India for its demand and trade between these two countries. In the 18th century, the artisans in the Uppada village of East Godavari district in Andhra Pradesh of India started to produce Jamdani sarees, recreated with a local quality (Karim and Karim, 2017) with the technique of weaving Jamdani from 'Bengali roots', and named as 'Uppada Jamdani', which is actually diaphanous silk saree, not same as Jamdani of Dhaka.

5. CURRENT MARKET SITUATION OF JAMDANI

5.1 Market Size

Currently the craft of weaving Jamdani is surviving in around 155 villages of Sonargaon, Rupganj, and Siddhirganj (Tabassum, 2021) area under Naryanganj

district of Dhaka division. At present there are around 2000 weavers in the BSCIC Jamdani industrial city and altogether 5000 weavers in Bangladesh. The industrial city produces and sells around 60,000 jamdani products, fetching around taka 36 crores. Moreover, the market outside this industrial city also trades around taka 5 to 6 crore per year (Tabassum, 2021). Altogether it is a big market inside the country. However, we came to know from weavers and retailers that recently local market is being flooded with Jamdani from India. These Indian Jamdani sarees are cheaper, mostly synthetic and machine weaved. Middle income customers and also customers who are not properly aware of the intricacy and design of Jamdani are buying these Indian Jamdani.

5.2 The Business Model

Informal discussion with the weaver families reveals that traditionally Jamdani weaving was a family-based occupation. Children used to start learning from an early age (10-12 years), help parents and other elderly members of the family to do the task. Now a days people outside of the weaver community, even people from other regions of the country come to the weavers to learn this skill. Usually large weavers having a good number of handlooms recruit these people. They start working as apprentice. Apprenticeship takes about 6 months to one year. During the apprentice period new (to be) weavers get food, shelter, and some allowance. However, new generation of the weaver families are moving away from weaving, because weavers usually get very minimum wage e.g., around Tk 25,000 per month. They cannot live a good life by weaving only. New generation of the families are focusing more on trading of Jamdani. They are exploring networks to sell directly to the consumers. They are installing large number (8-12) of hand-looms and employing other weavers (15-20) to increase production.

As majority of the craftsman are poor, they don't have any sales center. They sell their products at the weekly 'Haat' which is maximum 60 x 80= 480 square feet space. The "Haat" starts early in the morning every Friday and continue for only couple of hours. The researchers visited the 'haat' and found out that the main buyers in "Haat" are wholesalers, some retailers and a number of well-off weavers who own and run a large number of handlooms. Businessmen who buy from the "haat" sell these items to different markets of Dhaka and other cities.

5.3 Investment, Cost of Production and Margin

By compiling information collected from the BSCIC personnel and a few large weaver families it is estimated that capital investment required to establish a weaving facility of the 8-12 hand-looms is around Tk 7-10 lac. Material cost is not high - around 15%-25% of revenue. However, the labor cost turns out to be 60%-70% of the revenue despite the substandard wage rate. The entrepreneur weaver/trader can hardly enjoy 5%-10% margin. If we take the cost of fund and selling and distribution expenses into account the net income for the owner become very low. Retailers usually buy the items on credit with 60 to 90 days term. Only a few big retailers purchase on cash.

some of the retailers have their own designers, they get the products weaved as per their design and color scheme. From this kind of large orders sometimes the loom owner/ weavers get advance payment. In such instances, they follow make to order model of operation.

6. JAMDANI'S POTENTIALS TOWARDS NATION BRANDING THROUGH SIMON ANHOLTS' MODEL OF NATION BRANDING

Anholt's hexagon of nation branding is one of the most widely used models in business literature. As we did google scholar search with keyword 'nation branding' and downloaded and reviewed about 56 relevant papers we have found that all of them have referred to Simon Anholt's Nation Branding Hexagon (Figure 1), which focuses on the nation as a whole – its people, culture and heritage, investment and immigration, governance, exports and tourism.

Figure 1 : Nation Branding Hexagon adopted from Anholt (1998)

In 2003, Anholt introduced Nations Brand Index (NBI) that ranks countries as per their score across these six core areas. The potentials of Jamdani towards nation branding is presented below using Anholt's Nation Branding Hexagon.

6.1 People

People aspect scores a nation in terms of general education level, openness, friendliness and other qualities of the population as well as perceived levels of hostility and discrimination in the nation.

The Sultan of Delhi Muhammad bin Tughlak brought some Persian weavers to weave Jamdani in the 14th century in this sub-continent. They ultimately migrated here and became the citizens of this sub-continent. Some of the weavers now claimed and believed that their ancestors were of Persian origin. However, now they have harmonized with the culture of this region.

Aesthetic skill is the most important skill of this community. These weavers themselves play the role of weavers as well as designers. They themselves decide the design, color, fabric (count of cotton) everything. Before weaving a saree, their artistic eyes understand its exclusiveness. They acquire this skill from their childhood when they start to give support to their parents as most of the weavers make saree at their own front yards or loom-sheds inside their homes. Presently almost 65,000 weavers are earning their livelihood from this trade. Generation after generation they are involved with this craft. Generally, they start their day in the very morning, normally from Fajr Prayer and continue up to evening. Sometimes they continue up to midnight, if required. On average, every craftsman spends their time not less than 12 to 14 hours per day and 72 to 84 hours per week. As anyone walks through the weaver's village he/she will hear the continuous clattering sound of the hand loom from the houses. The sound goes on from dawn to dusk. Barely any one will be seen loitering aimlessly or sitting idle. This represents the hardworking nature of the population in the community.

In general, the weaver community represents the closely tied families of Bangladesh irrespective of their religion, caste, social status and political beliefs. The community represents the peace loving, hospitable people of the country. So, the livelihood of the people involved with the trade and the social fabric of the community have the potential to contribute to the people dimension of NBI.

6.2 Governance

Governance aspect measures the public opinion regarding competency and fairness of national government, as well as perceived commitment of a nation's government to certain universally important issues such as democracy, justice, poverty alleviation and the environment conservation.

The government of Bangladesh has rightly pointed out the potential of Jamdani in the global market. One of the prominent initiatives taken by the government to protect and promote this heritage is the establishment of a Jamdani Industrial Estate & Research Centre.

Most of the Jamdani artisans live in Narayanganj district near Dhaka in areas such as Noapara, Dakkhin Ruposhi, Ruposhi Kajipara, Gandabpur, Shiddhirgonj, Mugrakul, Khidirpur, Imkoli, Tarabo, Khalpara, Dighborar, Khadun, Pabankul, Sultanbagh and some areas of Sonargaon upazila. Government owned organization, Bangladesh small and cottage industries corporation (BSCIC) conducted a number of longitudinal studies on Jamdani weavers and the progression of the trade (Figure 2).

(Adopted from BSCIC periodical surveys on handlooms)

Figure 2 : Number of Operating Hand Loom Units Over the Years

It is evident that the number of handloom units in operation were declining since 1962-63. It started to rise only when the government intervened through BSCIC. Starting in 1993, BSCIC completed building Jamdani Industrial Estate and Research Centre in 1999, in Noapara village in Narayangonj district at a cost of Tk 58.563 million across a land of 20 acres. About 407 industrial plots (each of about 1500 square feet) over 14.39 acres of land has been allotted to weaver-entrepreneurs. This initiative of the government has so far been a vantage ground for the artisans. As of 2017, about 3000-3500 weavers run the 1750 hand loom units in the Jamdani Industrial state and annually produce fabrics worth TK 12-15 crores. In 2020, the estate's entrepreneurs earned around Tk 30 crore to Tk 32 crore by selling around 60,000 pieces of sari, salwar kameez, panjabi, screens, neckties etc. The objective of the industrial state is to enhance the production quality and marketing, supply designs and samples that are likely to have high demand in markets and conduct research on improving qualitative standards. But somehow over the last two decades, it seems the project has lost its focus.

Recent visits to the estate reveal that development and maintenance work is inadequate in the area. The roads are dilapidated, sewerage and water distribution networks are very rudimental. BSCIC officials alleged that the entrepreneurs who have got industrial spots are not following the rules laid by the BSCIC. There are plentiful examples of how the heritage and craft of a particular region can contribute in creating a nation's identity through ample governance of the region and the trade as a whole. Therefore, the bottom line is that the area where this unique craftsmanship take place should be developed and maintained in a way to portray sustainability, safety, and a unique ambience to feel and appreciate the art, craft and its underlying legacy, history and story.

Another useful intervention of the government has been the persuasion for a Geographical Indication (GI) certificate for our Jamdani Fabric. Bangladesh has got GI on Jamdani in 2016. Furthermore, UNESCO has declared the distinct method of weaving Jamdani as a world heritage. After the recognition of Jamdani as the GI product, 66 weavers have been given the GI certificates by the Bangladesh Small and Cottage Industries Corporation (BSCIC). But they do not have any idea about

how they can be benefited from GI (primary source) as they have not received ample training, guidelines, and framework to use the tags in the production and marketing of Jamdani. There is even a paucity of relevant metrics such as the number of tagged items sold so far, the countries where the exports have been made, the customer satisfaction, etc. (Halder, 2021).

However, big retailers such as Aarong, Kumudini, and some shop owners at Sunrise Plaza, Dhaka are found to be aware of GI. But they too are not sure how they can benefit from GI. This indicates that although it has been more than 5 years since we have received the GI, we have not been able to reap any big gain from it in the global markets. Therefore, the Government should come up with proper guidelines, policies and support to reap the benefits of GI.

6.3 Exports

In terms of exports, a country is scored based on the image of its products and services and the extent to which consumers proactively seek or avoid products of the country.

Although Jamdani is highly accoladed and has already garnered a tremendous reputation in the local market, its true potential in the global market is yet to be tapped (Aiman, 2021). Sales of Jamdani in the international market is concentrated in India (around \$6.5 million in 2011) and some other South Asian countries. A large volume also goes to Bangladeshi, Indian and South Asian immigrants in Europe, Middle East and North America. Jamdani sari worth Tk 0.12 billion was sold on spot in the International Jamdani Taant Bastra Mela (Handloom Textile Fair) organized by Bangladesh Weavers Product and Manufacturing Business Association (BWPMB) in 2011. Total export of Jamdani from Bangladesh was \$4.84 million and \$10.41 million in 2008-09 and 2010-11 respectively. These numbers indicate that the popularity of Jamdani in the international market was flourishing in the last decade. But no official estimate of recent (over this decade) sales of Jamdani in the international market is available. From our interview with some traders in the weekly 'Haat' at Noapara, Narayanganj, it is revealed that a number of large Indian buyers buys Jamdani from the 'Haat' and/or directly from the weavers and resell them to Indian consumers using an informal channel. A good number of Jamdani sarees also are sent to customers abroad via mail either by the customers' relatives or friends or by the retailers themselves. This is also not a formal channel of selling. Jamdani is also sent abroad by the state as official gifts to foreign delegates. Hence, if proper policies are formulated and implemented and bi-lateral trade agreements are negotiated with the destination countries, Jamdani can be one of the significant sources of export earnings for Bangladesh.

In this regard, getting GI certification is a positive step forward to excel in the export market to build a reputation, ensure fair price, and broader access to the larger marketplace. In fact, it assures the authenticity of origin and manufacturers.

6.4 Tourism

The level of interest of the tourists in visiting a country for its natural and man-made attractions determines the tourism score in the NBI.

In many countries, handcraft is important for local tourism and can act as an alternative source of income for the local people. Handcraft is one of the most noticeable and significant symbols of the cultural identity of a nation (Mevhibe & Ozdemir, 2012).

Jamdani weavers'/ artisans' livelihood, their life stories, unique craftsmanship and even localized technologies can be showcased to attract tourists. Even the weekly Jamdani Haat that starts at dawn on Friday ends within two hours. Local weavers come to the Haat with freshly finished fabric to sell to the big buyers. This Haat has its own colorful, crowded, busy ambience. Weavers show off their work by holding the fabrics up above their head and waving them to draw attention of the buyers. They also call buyers by declaring the significant features of the fabrics and asking price aloud. This 'Haat', representing the local market culture, can be a place of visitation for the tourists.

Present Government has taken initiatives by giving spaces for weaver families and named the area as 'BASIC Jamdani Industrial State'. As mentioned earlier, the weavers do the weaving in their homes, visiting the households in the area can be of interest to the tourists. Visitors will get a feel of the context /origin of a delicate product that they would love to possess. Visitation in the community will also communicate the tale of livelihood of the craftsmen. Different tour operators have already included this area as part of 'Day Tour' around Dhaka city.

6.5 Culture and Heritage

Culture and Heritage are the image of a community that transfer from generation to generation. According to the International Council on Monuments and Sites (ICOMOS), heritage includes customs, practices, places, objects, artistic expressions and values and so on, which entail from both tangible and intangible elements. Tangible elements include: art, memorabilia, artifacts, clothing, food, physical spaces, products, landscapes, buildings and many more. Intangible elements include customs, tradition, values, beliefs, language, achievements, history, religion and skills (Ahmad, 2006). As per Jamdani, the fabric, its inherent fineness, inherited floral and geometric themes from the Mughal dynasty and before, and the intricate hand-made designs are the tangible elements of heritage. Moreover, the technology and tools used in weaving- the hand loom, choroka etc. are the symbol of local heritage. Historically, Jamdani is a delicate party wear for the King/ Nawab/Emperors' families, carrying the legacy of the elite class. Even these days, the person wearing a high quality Jamdani on any occasion are considered to be an elegant aristocrat. Bangladeshi women and even the women of some provinces of India wear Jamdani saree on special occasions. Hence, Jamdani represents a specific culture and heritage of Bengal.

Heritage cycle (Figure 2) conceptualized by Thurley (2005) presents how a product associated with a particular culture and heritage is propagated across communities and generations. In the first stage of the cycle, the prospective consumer identifies and understands the culture and heritage; in the second stage they value it, then they care for it and enjoy it; finally, they feel the thirst to understand it further.

Figure 3 : Heritage Cycle Adopted from Thurley (2005)

Researchers of this study have observed from their surroundings and their personal experiences that Jamdani buyers quickly fall in this heritage cycle. Once someone gets acquainted with the culture and heritage associated with Jamdani, she/he usually values it. Upon using this, she/he feels the delicacy, enjoys it and becomes enticed to explore more about it. That is why Jamdani, although started its journey in 320 BC, is still a fondly desired fabric of attire of the new generation Bengalis.

6.6 Investment and Immigration

It estimates the power of a nation to attract people to live, work or study in a country and reveals how people perceive a country's economic and social situation.

Jamdani has the potential to attract people from across the globe to come and live in Bangladesh at least for a short term. If Jamdani as a fabric becomes popular in other countries (beyond India where it is already popular), the government of Bangladesh, private sector companies, non-government organizations (NGOs) can approach foreign investors to provide funding to boost up the sector.

Moreover, Bangladesh has got geographical indication (GI) in 2016. Bangladesh can also explore getting foreign funds to formulate policies and guidelines to implement GI and train the traders and weavers regarding ways to realize the benefits of GI. Even, foreign brands involved in the business of clothing and luxury goods may become interested in making investment in the sector if the potentials of the sector are effectively promoted in the international market.

Based on the analysis presented above, it is evident that Jamdani has immense possibilities in branding Bangladesh. It has the potential to uplift all six dimensions

of the nation brand as proposed by Anholt (1998). In order to strengthen our assertion from this section, the following section presents some evidence about how GI products like our Jamdani can contribute to nation branding.

7. HOW GI PRODUCTS CAN CONTRIBUTE IN NATION BRANDING

A geographical indication (GI) used on a product that has a particular geographical origin and possesses a reputation globally. GI is part of branding any product or place based on the cultural, natural, and traditional attractions and the uniqueness of the products that shape the local identity (Rahmah, 2014). GI certification is a sort of stamp guaranteeing the authenticity of the cultural heritage and unique localized craftsmanship, skill set and knowledge associated with the product. Marketing GI products in the global market, thereby, is a way to let the world know about the unique heritage, specialties of the product and its origin. The image of a country is the summation of impressions and beliefs people hold about a certain place or a country, which shapes peoples' perception about products or services from that place, investors' attitude regarding whether to invest, and tourists' expectations about the experience to have (Kenzhalina, 2013). Proper marketing and branding of GI products can attract not only tourists but also educationists, researchers, historians, entrepreneurs and investors from different destinations. For example, studies have found that countries benefit from the food products with GI labels (Başkaya, 2020), tourism potentials of any area with GI labels infrastructure (Misra, 2021). Hence, GI products have a significant contribution in boosting the image of a country across the borders (IŞIK & BİLİCİ, 2021). In fact, studies have found that countries are recalled with their localized food items, and this can contribute to the branding of cities.

8. A ROAD MAP TO BRAND JAMDANI

It is evident from our analysis presented so far that Jamdani, if marketed properly as such to establish a successful unique brand, will automatically contribute to our national brand. This section therefore presents a road map to brand Jamdani.

Branding activity is important to get recognition in the market, differentiate the offerings, and have legal protections. In fact, brand level assets permit firms to charge a premium price for their products or services (Agarwal & Barone, 2005). To brand any product or service, we need to follow some steps. Baliga, Joshi, and Shenoy (2019) provided a step-by-step framework for branding strategy. As per their framework there are four broad steps of branding, i.e., (i) consumer segmentations and positioning, (ii) protection strategy, (iii) brand awareness campaigns, and (iv) brand associations and judgment. These steps are highly interrelated; later steps are built on the foundations of preceding steps. Again, brand building blocks proposed by Keller, Parameswaran and Jacob (2015) provide a detailed manifestation of the later three steps of branding strategy. Hence, the branding road map we are presenting here starts with segmentation, targeting and positioning and then moves on the Keller, Parameswaran and Jacob's (2015) building block.

8.1 Market Segmentation, Targeting, and Positioning (STP)

The preliminary objective of STP is to subgroup customers with unique features and position the brand into their minds (Jewel & Kalam, 2020). According to Kotler and Armstrong (2018), “Market segmentation means dividing the market into distinct groups of buyers who have different needs, characteristics, or behaviors and who might require separate marketing strategies or mixes”. For the Jamdani product, first, we need to segment the market based on the customers’ needs, and the most attractive markets or segments should be targeted. The targeting strategies can be undifferentiated (considering everyone is the potential customer), differentiated (targeting several segments with separate offers for each), concentrated (targeting to obtain a large share of a niche segment), or micromarketing (catering the needs and wants of individual customers) (Grewal & Levy, 2017). From these four strategies, we recommend that Jamdani follow the concentrated targeting strategies as this product requires special soft skills, favorable environment, extreme care, and significant time to produce, therefore, it is expensive too. Considering these, it cannot be a brand for everyone, rather this study recommends that it be positioned as a luxury product. According to Kotler and Keller (2012), “Positioning is the act of designing a company’s offering and image to occupy a distinctive place in the minds of the target market”. While positioning as a luxury item will help reap the benefit from the market, doing so calls for a meticulous strategy.

Therefore, having the market segmented and target market identified, this study proposes following the brand building blocks provided by Keller, Parameswaran and Jacob (2015) to develop a robust branding for the Jamdani. Figure 3 shows the model along with the specific sub dimensions relevant to the branding of Jamdani and the major objectives to achieve at each stage.

8.2 Keller, Parameswaran and Jacob’s (2015) Brand Building Blocks

Figure 4 : Brand Resonance Pyramid (Keller et al., 2015) with Sub-Dimensions

The left side of the above model contains the ‘rational path’ to brand building while the right side shows the ‘emotional path’. Each block in the model and how that can be capitalized to brand ‘Made-in Bangladesh’ Jamdani is explained below-

8.2.1 Creation of Brand Salience

The major objective of this step is to create a broad and deep awareness about the Jamdani in the target customers' mind. In creating awareness, the emphasis should be on the Jamdani fabric (not just Saree), so that whenever buyers think of buying fine quality clothes, they consider the items made of Jamdani fabric, which can be used to produce various types of clothes. Now to develop such a brand image, an awareness campaign through multiple media should be launched. For instance, advertisements in targeted global fashion magazines, international broadcast channels such as BBC and CNN, use of suitable celebrity with a fresh image, taking part in pertinent international trade shows, etc. are some of the viable options. Apart from them, use of social media, such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and YouTube may play a vital role to reach the target audience with core messages at a low cost. However, a coordinated effort and a well thought plan are instrumental to ensure a successful awareness creation program, which, in turn, create a positive emotion about the brand and keep the brand apart from competitions. This study suggests that the focus be made on the unique expertise of the weavers of Bangladesh and the rich history of Bangladeshi Jamdani. Thus, to create that broad and deep awareness, this study proposes the following more specific ideas.

KEYWORD SELECTION : To represent Jamdani as a luxury item, it is instrumental to use some specific keywords in the communication that connote exclusivity, rarity, heritage, etc. Upon studying the history of Jamdani and talking to the weavers in-person, this study suggests some words or phrases that might be used: "100% handmade", "The ultimate royalty", "hundreds-of-year-experience" etc.

BRAND ELEMENTS : Brand elements are strong devices to create a strong brand awareness, and form a strong, positive, and exclusive brand association (Keller, 2013), such as URLs, logos, symbols, characters, slogans, jingles, packages, signage, and spokespeople.

Brand elements should be meaningful, memorable, likable, adaptable, transferable, and should be protectable as registered trademark. It is important because in the absence of intellectual property rights, the spurious products take the advantage of old fame (Bhat and Singh, 2017). Having said that, the visual aspect of the brand elements requires special care. To improve quality perceptions and boost international image, visual stimuli should play a vital role (Henderson et al., 2003). In one study, to brand the "Kashmir Saffron", Saqib (2015) emphasized on the use and importance of a graphic symbol that can point to a GI.

DESIGN OF SLOGAN/TAGLINE : Having some interesting taglines or slogans centering on a key idea is highly important for luxury brands. For the product in discussion, luxury is the center point. Along with that, this paper proposes some taglines as well: "There is no alternative to a Jamdani", "Jamdani: the true royalty you can wear", "Every style/design of Jamdani carries a rich history", etc.

CREATION OF A LOGO : Creative logos have historically been successful to represent brands globally that can be used across cultures. Thus, this study recommends that a logo be designed, trademarked, and used on original ‘made in Bangladesh’ Jamdani items. Moreover, a clear guideline on proper use of the logo should follow. Of all the brand elements, the logo offers some added advantages. Since logos can be transferred across language, nationalities, and age groups, it becomes the most memorable brand element. Moreover, in comparison to other brand elements such as background music and jingle, logos have widespread appeal with regard to the target market and usage with regard to communication platforms (Aggarwal, Singh and Prashar, 2014).

PACKAGING AND ‘MADE-IN-BANGLADESH’ TAG : There should also be well-designed packaging with a premium image, such as, the logo, the rich history and tradition of the product, guidelines to use and maintain Jamdani for durability, etc. It should be obligatory that the visual elements are displayed on the specific space of the packaging and all authorized users of the package follow the specifications strictly (Aggarwal, Singh and Prashar, 2014). Furthermore, each item should have a product tag. The tag should include the logo and “Made-in-Bangladesh” phrase which will reinforce the authenticity of the product. Moreover, it should also have information about the meaning of the design and style used, time (in hours) and manpower required to produce that particular item, and the portion of profit that will be spent for the welfare of the weavers.

BRAND STORY : Stories, if relevant to the brand, are highly powerful to raise awareness and create association with the product. Since Jamdani has a rich history and tradition, this study highly recommends to develop multiple brand stories that talk about the glorious past of Jamdani, such as how these were used to be produced with utmost care by highly skilled weavers and worn by selective royal families, how the craftsmanship has been transferred from generation to generation, etc. The ultimate purpose of doing so is to associate Jamdani products with factual and interesting stories so that customers trust the claimed expertise of Bangladeshi weavers.

8.2.2 Brand Performance

Since the product will be branded as a luxury item, it should be ensured that the product has the top-notch performance. Therefore, Jamdani fabric should not just meet the requirement only but it should aim to exceed them and it, in return, will establish customer loyalty. The Jamdani fabrics made in Bangladesh offer the best performance as they are finely finished on both sides with no coarse left on either side. Unlike machine-made Jamdani, such handmade fabric is very comfortable to wear. Since it is an exclusive product benefit that no other competitors can offer, it can be used as a strong point of differentiation. Another important part of this block is price which itself signals quality. Since preparation of this fine fabric is an arduous job and requires significant time, extreme caution and patience, this study recommends that Jamdani fabric be priced in the premium range. Moreover, to maintain the luxury image, the brand should not offer any sort of discount.

8.2.3 Brand Imagery

Here the goal is to fulfill customers' psychological and social needs by focusing on the intangible aspects of the brand. There are multiple ways that brands can capitalize on to create strong imagery. For Jamdani, this imagery can be developed by highlighting the hundreds of years of history, culture, heritage, and tradition of weaving the fabric. The focus on the product history which has its root to ancient past will be helpful to create trust in the brand. Again, to compete with the strong players in the global market, it is a good strategy for the small players from the developing country to link the product with the culture and history of the area of production (Mancini, 2013). As suggested earlier, a successful way of informing customers about these intangible aspects is through brand story which creates strong association between the product and its rich history.

8.2.4 Brand Judgment

Successful branding requires understanding the customers' personal opinions and evaluations. Brand users make judgments about product quality, trustworthiness, consideration and superiority. Customers will form an attitude towards the quality of an apparel item based on the comfort to wear, design, style, and appearance, etc. Efforts towards exceeding these criteria over customers' expectations will ensure customers' favorable judgment towards Jamdani. Highlighting that only Bangladeshi weavers have the competency to produce this fabric will ensure trustworthiness. More importantly, brand stories centering on the history will bolster the claim of unique expertise. Making customers consider the brand for purchase is challenging, as the positivity towards quality and credibility may not always translate into purchases. Hence, this study suggests further action. For instance, a portion of profit from the sale of Jamdani should be spent to train and educate the weavers and enhance their living standards, etc. A brand resonating with a strong social cause will have a higher audience, specially from the younger generation.

8.2.5 Brand Feelings

Brand feelings are the customers' emotional response to the brand and its marketing programs. According to the brand building pyramid, these feelings are: warmth, fun, excitement, security, social-approval, and self-respect. For Jamdani, the branding drives should attempt to evoke feelings of warmth, social-approval, and self-respect. The campaigns should focus on a comfortable feeling (a sense of warmth) that one may enjoy upon wearing Jamdani products. It has to be branded so that wearing Jamdani products makes customers feel like royalty, which will invoke social approval and self-respect.

8.2.6 Brand Resonance

This is the pinnacle of the brand building block pyramid, which Jamdani should reach gradually. It explains the nature of the relationship customers have with the brand. Here, the focus of Jamdani branding should be to create a 'sense of community'

among the consumers. With an increase in the engagement on social media, this study recommends creation of an online community of customers, where global customers may share their experiences of wearing Jamdani, or how Jamdani fabric can be tailored to their native-wear. An active engagement will generate a positive attitude towards this product, build up a sense of ownership among the customers, and create a loyal customer base.

9. CONCLUSION

This paper has identified the unique feature and cultural heritage associated with Jamdani. By analyzing Jamdani through the lense of Anholt's nation branding hexagon this paper concludes that 'Jamdani' fabrics have very intricated hand-made designs and specific themes resembling the long dated cultural heritage of the country it can be placed in the global market place not only as a unique product but also as a source of distinct cultural heritage. Jamdani weavers' / artisans' livelihood, their life stories, unique craftsmanship and even localized technologies can be showcased to attract tourists. If the country can market 'Jamdani' effectively, it can also attract flow of foreign funds. Jamdani thus has immense potential to contribute to Branding Bangladesh. This paper also provides a detailed road map to brand Jamdani in the world market which may be considered as a guideline for Jamdani traders and other stakeholders. This paper also makes unique contribution to branding literature by analyzing a particular product through the lens of nation branding model and assimilating product/service branding strategies with nation branding. However, the findings of the qualitative inquiry must be used with caution. The conclusion drawn here may not be generalizable, the road map presented here can not be replicated as it is in practice. In order to, formulate specific operational strategies and action plans for nation branding through Jamdani, extensive market research should be done.

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